

IMPROVED SYNTHESIS OF 3:4-BENZOPYRENE-5-C¹⁴*

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Synthesis of 3:4-benzopyrene-5-C¹⁴ has been achieved in a greater overall yield by modifications of the existing methods. Preparation of perinaphthene (III) of high purity in better yield from perinaphthanone-7 (VI) is also recorded.

In an extended study of the nature of the protein-bound acidic metabolite and its mode of formation on the skin after painting the test animals with the highly carcinogenic 3:4-benzopyrene (Tarbell *et al.*, *Cancer Res.*, 1956, 16, 37), it became necessary to label the same hydrocarbon (I) at position 5 with C¹⁴. Although the known synthetic route (Heidelberger and Reike, *ibid.*, 1951, 11, 640; Fieser and Hershberg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 1658) (Chart I) was essentially followed, it is intended to record here some useful modifications developed, which improve the yield and simplify the procedure.

Following the recorded methods (*loc. cit.*; Boekelheide and Larrabee, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1240), we could not obtain the key material, perinaphthene (III), from perinaphthanone-7 (VI) in high yields with the high purity required for the radioactive synthesis. Attempted high pressure hydrogenation of perinaphthanol-7 (VII), the metal hydride reduction product of the

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ketone over copper chromite at 230° with varying amounts of catalyst (Boekelheide and Goldman, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 575), did not result in more than 30-50% yield of the crude hydrocarbon. Finally, the hydrogenolysis of perinaphthanone-7 (VI) or the corresponding alcohol in methanol in presence of 10% Pd-C at ordinary temperature and pressure and purification through the picrate, m.p. 150-51°, provided perinaphthane of desired purity, m.p. 65-65.5°, in 70% yield.

With some manipulative modifications the synthesis of 2:1'-trimethylene-1:9-benzanthrone-10-C¹⁴, m.p. 218.5-20°, in brilliant yellow leaflets proceeded smoothly.

Attempted conversion of the ketone to the hydrocarbon in stages was not very promising. Thereupon a variety of conditions was tried for the distillation of the ketone over activated zinc with a view to improving the yield. The best method has been recorded in the Experimental section. 3:4-Benzopyrene-5-C¹⁴ obtained in 37% overall yield, based on benzoic acid-carbonyl-C¹⁴, is the highest yield reported so far.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Preparation of Perinaphthanol-7 (VII) by the Sodium Borohydride Reduction of Perinaphthanone-7 (VI).—Perinaphthanone-7 (3 g.), obtained in about the same yield recorded in the literature by the chloromethylation of naphthalene by Coles and Dodds' method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 853) and then following Fieser and Gates' (*ibid.*, 1940, **62**, 2335), was dissolved in ethanol (15 c.c.) to which sodium borohydride (1 g.) was added, and the mixture was left overnight. It was worked up in the usual way and on recrystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether, long stout colorless needles of perinaphthanol-7 in clusters (2.9 g.), m.p. 84-85°, were obtained. The mixed m.p. with a sample prepared by the LiAlH₄ reduction of the ketone (Boekelheide and Larrabee, *ibid.*, 1950, **72**, 1245) showed no depression. Quantitatively, the former method was found to be better.

Preparation of Perinaphthane (III): (a) By the Hydrogenolysis of Perinaphthanol-7 (VII) over 10% Pd-C Catalyst (cf. Boekelheide and Goldman, *loc. cit.*).—Perinaphthanol-7 (10 g.) was dissolved in methanol (100 c.c.) and was shaken with hydrogen over 10% Pd-C catalyst, prepared according to Mozingo ("Organic Syntheses", 1946, Vol. 26, p.77), at ordinary temperature and pressure until no more absorption was observed. After removal of the catalyst and the solvent, the residue was taken up in ether and converted into the picrate, which on recrystallisation from methanol yielded orange-red needles (13.3 g.), m.p. 151-52°. The picrate on decomposition through alumina afforded pure, free hydrocarbon (5.7 g.), m.p. 65-65.5°, in 62% yield.

(b). By Hydrogenolysis of Perinaphthanone-7 (VI) over Pd-C Catalyst.—Perinaphthanone-7 (10 g.) was dissolved in methanol (75 c.c.) and hydrogenated over 10% Pd-C at ordinary temperature and pressure. The hydrogenation was complete within 12 hrs. It was worked up as outlined before to yield 6.4 g. of perinaphthane (70%), m.p. 65-65.5°.

Attempted hydrogenolysis of the acetic acid solution (30 c.c.) of the ketone (2 g.) in a Parr apparatus over 5% Pd-C (1 g.) at an initial pressure of 37 lbs. and at 65° according to Horning and Reisner (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1036) yielded a colorless oil (1.5 g.), b.p. 77°/0.5 mm. The oil did not form any picrate. The infrared spectrum of the liquid, however, showed the absence of the carbonyl peak. It might therefore be a ring-reduced product formed as a result of overhydrogenation. It was not investigated further.

* Melting points are uncorrected unless otherwise stated. Fisher adsorption alumina and petroleum ether (b.p. 30-60°) have been used throughout. The micro-analyses are in good agreement with the theory. The radioactive assays were done by the wet combustion followed by C¹⁴-measurements by ionisation chamber technique using a Vibrating Reed Electrometer, Applied Physics Corporation (U.S.A.), Model No. 31.

Preparation of 3-Benzoylperinaphthane-carbonyl-C¹⁴ (IV).—Benzoyl chloride-carbonyl-C¹⁴ (1.261 g.) was prepared from benzoic acid-carbonyl-C¹⁴ (containing 12.53 mc. of radioactivity) according to Heidelberger and Reike (*loc. cit.*) in about the same yield, except that the benzene was removed at ordinary pressure at a bath temperature of 130-40°. It was diluted with unlabelled benzoyl chloride (0.7 g.); the carbonyl disulphide solution of the Perrier complex with aluminium chloride (1.92 g.) was added from a warm funnel to a solution of perinaphthane (2.27 g.) in the same solvent (the reverse addition decreased the yield to some extent) and worked up according to the recorded procedures (*loc. cit.*). The pale yellow, highly viscous 3-benzoylperinaphthane-carbonyl-C¹⁴ (3.085 g.) distilled at 218-20°/0.1 mm. From the sides and the cold finger of the still a further amount (0.574 g.) was recovered. The total yield was 96%.

Preparation of 2:1'-Trimethylene-1:9-benzanthrone-10.—It was prepared from benzoylperinaphthane (2.1 g.) in the same way as by Heidelberger and Reike (*loc. cit.*) excepting the modification mentioned below. After the reaction was over, the melt was poured into ice and HCl (1:1). Most of the melt, however, solidified in the reaction flask, which was scraped off, gradually decomposed, and left overnight. The product, collected at the bottom of the clear solution, was extracted with chloroform. The organic layer was washed, dried, and the solvent concentrated to a small volume. On addition of petroleum ether and keeping overnight, the dirty grey, granular mass (1.15 g.), easy to handle, was obtained. Further purification was effected by chromatography over alumina or by short-path distillation at 230-40°/0.1 mm. Crystallisations from benzene-acetone or precipitation with petroleum ether from chloroform solution yielded golden yellow flakes, m.p. 218.5-20° (corr.).

Attempted Reduction of the 2:1'-Trimethylene-1:9-benzanthrone-10 with LiAlH₄.—The ketone (0.39 g.) was treated with LiAlH₄ in tetrahydrofuran in the usual way. Crystallisation from benzene-methanol yielded orange leaflets, m.p. 216-218.5° (corr.). (Found: C, 88.42; H, 5.14. Calc. for C₂₀H₁₆O: C, 88.20; H, 5.92%; for C₂₀H₁₄O: C, 88.86; H, 5.22%).

Attempted Dehydrogenation of the LiAlH₄ Reduction Product: (i) With 10% Pd-C.—The crude product (0.2 g.) was thoroughly mixed with 10% Pd-C (0.4 g.) and heated under an atmosphere of dry nitrogen at 340-60° for 3 hrs. Some yellow glistening crystals collected at the cooler part. The benzene solution of the product was chromatographed through alumina and directly converted into picrate of benzopyrene (Cook *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 396), m.p. 197-99°, but the yield was too poor (13 mg.) for this method to have any practical value.

(ii). *With 30% Pd-C.*—The substance (0.2 g.) was mixed with 30% Pd-C (Linstead and Thomas, *ibid.*, 1940, 1127) and heated at 35-55° for 3 hrs. The crude product was dissolved in benzene, to which petroleum ether was added. Long yellow needles embedded in the viscous oil separated. The m.p. of the crude product was above 220°. No further work was done with it.

Preparation of Benzopyrene-5-C¹⁴ (I).—2:1'-Trimethylene-1:9-benzanthrone-10-carbonyl-C¹⁴ (V), prepared in 82% yield from 3-benzoylperinaphthane-carbonyl-C¹⁴ (3.658 g.) by the precipitation method (*vide supra*), was distilled over activated zinc in three batches.

In a typical run, an intimate mixture of the ketone (1.039 g.) with 30 mesh activated zinc (Beerboom *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3500; Fieser and Johnson, *ibid.*, 1940, 62, 576) was introduced in the centre of a specially heat-resistant pyrex combustion tube (300 × 17 mm) and plugged with glass wool. A layer of activated zinc dust was made at both ends and plugged again. Dry nitrogen was passed through the tube, which was then introduced in a preheated (700°) furnace, while the stream of nitrogen continued. A tube from the other end was led through a

series of traps. The first two were cooled by dry ice-acetone and the last two contained benzene. All the connections were made as quickly as possible and the tube outside the furnace was cooled with wet cotton. Shortly after, heavy fumes were given off and dirty yellow distillate was collected at the cooler part. The operation was complete within 20 mins. The distillate was dissolved in ether; the residue was extracted with ether in a Soxhlet overnight and next with chloroform (to recover any unconverted starting material). The combined ether solution was concentrated and converted into the picrate. Recrystallisation from methanol yielded 1.316 g. (corresponding to 71% of benzopyrene based on the wt. of the ketone) of the crystallised material.

The total picrate from all the runs on two recrystallisations from the same solvent yielded 3.046 g. of dark purplish needles (corresponding to 1.596 g. of benzopyrene theoretically and 47% yield from 3-benzoylperinaphthane-carbonyl-C¹⁴), m.p. 198-99° (Cook *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The overall yield of the pure benzopyrene picrate, and hence that of benzopyrene based on benzoic acid-carbonyl-C¹⁴ is 37% containing the total radioactivity 6.134 mc. and specific activity 0.968 mc./m. moles respectively. We are unable to offer any satisfactory explanation for the observed higher activities.

A portion of the picrate (0.505 g.) was decomposed in the dark through a column (3×10 cm) of alumina using benzene as the solvent and eluent. The recovery of the hydrocarbon (0.227 g.) from the picrate was 86%. Recrystallisations from ethanol yielded yellow leaflets (0.15 g.) of benzopyrene, m.p. 176-77° (Cook *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), identified by the direct comparison with the purest sample available in our laboratory (Tarbell *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). For animal experiments, further chromatographic purification was done according to Heidelberger and Reike (*loc. cit.*).

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